

INTEGER

INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION
ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

D5.1 COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND STAKEHOLDERS' ENGAGEMENT PLAN

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Deliverable 5.1 - Communication, dissemination and stakeholders' engagement plan describes the engagement and outreach plan (E&O plan) and includes a clear communication policy, detailed map of the target audiences and key messages, appropriate dissemination channels, communication calendar, resources, and responsibilities of the partners in the INTEGER project.

Also, this deliverable defines dissemination activities for each partner to best exploit their contacts, networks and capabilities. It details the expected target groups and, for each of them, dissemination activities such as the project website and working platform, theglocal.network and selected social networks, dissemination materials, open access publications, targeted presentations, outreach events, stakeholders' exploitation workshops, and participatory collaboration opportunities.

This plan is a living document that will be updated at the end of each year, based on the analysis and monitoring results of implemented actions.

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SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
INTEGER	Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions
T	Task
WP	Work-Package
i2CAT	FUNDACIO PRIVADA I2CAT, INTERNET I INNOVACIO DIGITAL A CATALUNYA
URV	UNIVERSITAT ROVIRA I VIRGILI
FURV	FUNDACIO URV
F6S	F6S NETWORK IRELAND LIMITED
HAM	BEHOERDE FUER ARBEIT, GESUNDHEIT, SOZIALES, FAMILIE UND INTEGRATION HAMBURG
UJ	UNIWERSYTET JAGIELLONSKI
KTP	KRAKOWSKI PARK TECHNOLOGICZNY SP ZOO
SHINE	SHINE 2EUROPE LDA
AFE	AFEDEMY, ACADEMY ON AGE-FRIENDLY ENVIRONMENTS IN EUROPE BV
E&O plan	Engagement and outreach plan
3 H	Triple Helix
4 H	Fourth Helix
CC BY	Creative Commons-licensed research

Table 1: Symbols, abbreviations, and acronyms

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and aim

Focused on challenge-driven promotion of healthy living and wellbeing, INTEGER will bring forward three important innovations for the development of more robust, sustainable, inclusive, and integrative European Union (EU) innovation ecosystems:

- The INTEGER 4 Helix Col.laboratory model to implement the next generation of living labs, the 'Col.laboratories',
- An EU Healthy Living Col.laboratory, a true network of networks' community with capacity to work on real social, tech and business-driven projects, and
- A new professional profile, the 'col.laber' or 'col.laboratory manager' as a multiplying agent of change of these integrated innovation ecosystems.

The three INTEGER reinforcing innovations will push fivefold breakthrough capacities for the integration of social innovation in EU innovation ecosystems:

- Boost win-win games between business and social oriented innovations addressing common challenges.
- Transform co-creation dynamics into disruptive and tangible new products, services or competencies.
- Co-design jointly public innovation policies.
- Develop capacity building of the new generation of socio-digital entrepreneurs and ecosystems' enablers, the 'col.labers', and
- Devise funding and investment mechanisms for social innovation start-ups and SMEs to develop and scale up game changing innovations.

'Col.laboratories' and 'col.labers' aim to embrace economic and social-driven innovation communities across the EU. Based on a peer-to-peer approach between business-driven and social-driven innovations, INTEGER seeks to accelerate transformative integration outcomes by creating new win-win games, local mission-driven synergies, ground-breaking coordination of actions, governance, implementation, uptaking and exploitation dynamics. The project INTEGER is running for 2 years, starting in February 2023, and is divided into 5 Work-packages.

Figure 1: Pert Diagram of INTEGER

ENGAGEMENT, OUTREACH, AND IMPACT MAXIMISATION (WP5) is a horizontal Work Package (WP) across the project lifetime, dedicated to support the overall aims of the project and mobilise and engage key stakeholders in Europe and beyond.

The specific objectives are to:

- a. **raise awareness** of all relevant stakeholders about project activities, as well as its assets and resources.
- b. **create engagement** and secure participation in activities among key stakeholders through a variety of initiatives and events.
- c. **secure participation** of the relevant stakeholders and target groups in integrating social innovation actors in European ecosystems.
- d. **reach out and enhance** collaboration with other relevant projects, initiatives and networks for a better outreach and sustainable impact, and e) enable uptake of the project results.

This is essential for the impact of the project, and that is why the INTEGER Consortium is fully engaged to communicate the concept, the activities, and the project results to successfully raise public awareness and plan for the uptake of the results.

Inside this WP, the **Task 5.1 Communication and dissemination plan and activities** will define the communication and dissemination strategy and framework for the exploitation of the knowledge generated by the project.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The Deliverable 5.1 - Communication, dissemination and stakeholders' engagement plan describes the engagement and outreach plan (E&O plan) and includes a clear **communication policy**, detailed **map of the target audiences**, and **key messages**, appropriate **dissemination channels**, **communication calendar**, **resources**, and **responsibilities of the partners**.

This plan will be updated at the end of each year, based on the analysis and monitoring results of implemented actions.

It consists of six sections, as follows:

1. Introduction
2. Dissemination summary and goals
3. INTEGER Key Message
4. Stakeholder Analysis & Engagement Plan
5. Communication & Dissemination Tools & Channels
6. Timetable for delivery of communication & dissemination activities
7. Conclusion

The Plan also contains supporting Appendices, namely Appendix 1: Initial list of specific target stakeholders.

1.3 Synergies with other tasks and deliverables

The Work Package 5 - ENGAGEMENT, OUTREACH, AND IMPACT MAXIMISATION is a transversal work package across the project lifetime, dedicated to support the overall aims of the project and mobilise and engage key stakeholders in Europe and beyond. The Deliverable 5.1 - Communication, dissemination and stakeholders' engagement plan will describe the methods and the tools to achieve this goal.

WP	Task	Deliverable	Due Date
WP 2 - LEARNING FOR 4H COLLABORATORY CO-CREATION	Task 2.1 Establish digital co-creation environments (the digital platform) for Best Practices Exchange	D2.2 – Collaborathon Report & Exploitation Plan	M5
	Task 2.2 Reinforce inter-ecosystem 3H & 4H dynamics between social entrepreneurs and stakeholders in each innovation ecosystem.		
	Task 2.3 European-wide Col.laborathon organisation and implementation.	D2.4 – Report on inter-ecosystem projects and best practices exchanged	M 12
	Task 2.4 Col.laborathon results exploitation		
WP4 – INTEGER 4H MODEL & EU HEALTHY LIVING COLLABORATORY DEPLOYMENT	Task 4.1 Gathering and systematisation of relevant information and material in the INTEGER platform hub.	D4.2 EU-wide INTEGER innovative community constituted	M19
	Task 4.2 Development of a comprehensive model to accelerate the integration and collaboration of social innovation actors and digital business entrepreneurial hubs.	D4.3 – INTEGER 4H col.laboratory comprehensive model: academic papers accepted in scientific publications	M22
	Task 4.3 Deployment and sustainability of the EU Healthy Living Collaboratory.	D4.4 Report on coordination actions with key related initiatives	M24

	Task 4.4 Interconnecting and exchange with the related initiatives, networks, communities, and projects		
WP5 – ENGAGEMENT, OUTREACH AND IMPACT MAXIMISATION	Task 5.1 Communication and dissemination plan and activities.	D5.2 Stakeholder liaison with relevant initiatives and impact monitoring report	M24
	Task 5.2 Stakeholder engagement and liaison with relevant initiatives.	D5.3 Communication, dissemination, and stakeholders' implementation report	M24
	Task 5.3 Impact monitoring and maximisation plan and activities		

Table 2: WP's, Tasks and Deliverables related to D5.1

2 DISSEMINATION SUMMARY AND GOALS

The Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholders' Engagement Strategy for INTEGER was initially defined as a preliminary approach during the proposal preparation, based on specific objectives designed to maximise the impact of the project both during and beyond the end of the funding period.

As planned, the project dissemination activities will be targeted to create awareness and make available knowledge and results of the project to relevant stakeholders, but mostly to foster win-win games and citizen participation that CONNECT and ENGAGE 4H stakeholders in social innovation ecosystems.

The overall goal of this Strategy and Plan is to communicate the project concept and activities and promote INTEGER to successfully raise public awareness and plan for the uptake of the results. It aims to ensure wide exposure and promotion of the project results to targeted stakeholders and the media and facilitate their use beyond the project's lifetime.

The INTEGER Consortium is fully engaged in implementing this broad strategy to boost the project outcomes and benefits, to reach the widest possible audience and to ensure the sustainability of the outputs developed in the project.

The following table explains the consortium idea for this strategy.

Figure 2: Building and enlarging the INTEGER community.

The dissemination and communication strategy is coordinated by SHINE and AFE and implemented collaboratively by the entire consortium.

As mentioned, to keep the strategy in line with the project development, the partners will monitor and provide relevant adjustments when necessary. Additionally, the project will be

continuously open to new opportunities of dissemination and the plan will be adapted and updated along the project and the associated activities redirected as new ideas and opportunities arise.

2.1 Communication versus dissemination

While communication and dissemination activities are often referred to collectively, it is important to distinguish between them and highlight the specific role played by each in the INTEGER project. To this aim, an initial comparison of other concepts is necessary, namely of the differences between OUTPUTS, OUTCOMES and RESULTS

Figure 3: Outputs, outcomes and results concepts

According to the European Commission (EC) - Research Executive Agency, the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities in the projects are complementary but not identical, as summarised below:

Figure 4: Communication vs Dissemination vs Exploitation:¹

2.2 Communication and Dissemination Objectives

The overall objectives for INTEGER communication and dissemination activities were thought and described in the application as one of the project's impact points. The following table briefly describes these two points:

	Objectives	Impact
	Raise awareness of all relevant stakeholders about project activities, as well as its assets and resources.	Stakeholders are being kept informed about the work progress and the results during the work process and beyond.
	Create engagement and secure participation in activities among key stakeholders through a variety of initiatives and events	The wider public and relevant stakeholder groups, such as academia, researchers and policy makers are informed of INTEGER's achievements and materials and act as replicators of knowledge in their own communities.

¹ European Commission. COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION WHY THEY ALL MATTER AND WHAT IS THE DIFFERENCE? Available in: <https://rea.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-11/Communication%2C%20Dissemination%20and%20%20Exploitation-2021.pdf>

	Secure participation of the relevant stakeholders and target groups in integrating social innovation actors in European ecosystems.	End-users and stakeholders are being made aware of the INTEGER tools and goals, which are promoted among the relevant stakeholders and their use towards the inclusion of end-users is encouraged.
	Reach out and enhance collaboration with other relevant projects, initiatives and networks.	Enable a sustainable impact and ensure exploration beyond the project period.
	Enable uptake of the project result.	Development of a result closer to what stakeholders need and guarantee of its application.

Table 3: Communication & Dissemination Objectives and Impact

2.3 Communication & Dissemination KPIs

The specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) of INTEGER communication and dissemination activities evolve as appropriate to each stage of the project. However, a preliminary list of the KPIs to be achieved is displayed in the table below (in green the KPIs already achieved):

Target Audiences	Activity/channel	Indicator/KPI	Goal
All	INTEGER Social Media	Number of Twitter followers	300
		Number of LinkedIn followers	300
		Number of articles featured in influencing Twitter handles	10
All	Local/regional/national press	Number of articles	10
RTO & universities, health & care, tech	Scientific publications	Number of papers accepted on international relevant journals	2

& service providers, industry	Non-scientific publications	Number of articles and interviews on online magazines, specialised portals and platforms	6
	Participation in conferences, exhibitions, virtual or F2F	Number of presentations/keynote speeches/panels/workshops featured in the programme of national and international conferences and events organised by other networks, multipliers, programmes and initiatives	10
All	Newsletters	Number of newsletter releases to the contacts included in the partners' mailing list + new subscribers reached via social media campaigning	6
All	Graphic materials	Number of infographic and visuals	20
		Number of leaflets distributed (2 versions: one preliminary focusing on goals and channels and an intermediate with spotlights on tools – English + pilots' languages)	1000
		Project official roll-up and poster	1
		Templates for scientific/exhibition posters, if needed	NA

Table 4: KPI's communication & dissemination

In Year 1, the key focus is on creating awareness of the INTEGER project through communication activities and some dissemination in scientific networks. This will refocus in Year 2 to target more scientific dissemination, intensifying awareness and scientific publications and promoting exploitation of INTEGER outputs and their further upscale and broader use.

2.4 INTEGER Key message

The Consortium has formulated the following INTEGER project message:

The innovative potential of INTEGER is to offer a tested innovation model for accelerating the integration of social innovation actors and digital business entrepreneurial hubs in three EU regions.

In Year 1, the key focus of communication activities was on creating awareness of the INTEGER project among the main user groups and dissemination in scientific networks.

Therefore, the key message for communications in the first year was simple and with non-technical language, so that stakeholders in any target group are able to grasp the overall aim of the INTEGER project.

This key message is complemented by several additional supporting messages as follows:

- Focused on challenge-driven promotion of healthy living, INTEGER aims to bring together actors from triple-helix (3H) and quadruple-helix (4H) systems to face common challenges: the “col.laboratories”, a next generation of living labs, a cooperative instrument based on a peer-to-peer approach between business-driven economic innovation and social-driven innovation.
- INTEGER: Integrating 3H and 4H models for a European Innovation Ecosystems transition
- INTEGER is developing a quadruple helix collaborative model to reinforce 3 regional innovation ecosystems and to ground the EU INTEGER Col.laboratory on Health and Wellbeing.

In year 2, more complex messages may be developed for scientific audiences, as well as targeted messages that allow to exploit the different outputs closer to each stakeholder.

2.5 INTEGER Dissemination leads

As WP5 leader, SHINE acts as the INTEGER Dissemination Manager, helping to build, grow and manage INTEGER's online presence.

These roles will focus on the following key areas:

- Action plan for communication: the Communication & Dissemination Plan (D5.1) will be continuously reviewed and updated to ensure the project's communication activities are effective and reaching the target audience.
- Creation and management of content: to create content, SHINE contacts the partners on a periodic basis to collect information that they wish to communicate on relevant INTEGER activities and events, any results for dissemination and the latest news in the field. This material is used to feed INTEGER's social networks, update the project website, and issue informative newsletters on INTEGER and related areas of interest.

Moreover, the Consortium produces — (at least) every month— project-related updates to the online channels.

- Monitoring and analytics to measure online activity: SHINE monitors INTEGER online activity and analyses the metrics produced by Google Analytics (website) and LinkedIn and Twitter Analytics. This analysis provides intelligence on e.g., what visitors are most interested in, where INTEGER content should be placed to get most views, where (which platform) users are most engaged, how effective the social networks are at driving visitors to the website, and the demographics of the audience. These insights help to continuously refine the Communications Plan so that it meets the objectives of the INTEGER project and reaches the target audience.
- Connecting with target audience: SHINE uses the INTEGER website and social media channels to connect with the target audience. The website is the main communication channel for showcasing the project to the general public, Twitter is the key platform for engaging with professionals, the scientific community and other EU projects and initiatives and LinkedIn is used to connect with professionals and other stakeholders interested in the project. SHINE will use the analytics behind these online tools to continuously update the Communications Plan.
- Besides that, a learning network will be developed by SHINE to upscale the communication and dissemination activities, to provide the project partners and stakeholders a common platform to share their research, new opportunities, and new digital solutions that can be advanced across the continent and that include writing of joint policy releases and blogs, participation in national, international and multiplier events, presence in international, regional, national, local and social media and publishing in scientific publications

2.6 Scientific dissemination

Through policy briefs, short reports, tools, guidelines and scientific publications (in open access and peer-reviewed journals) it will be possible to translate knowledge, empirical and operational data into policies to inform stakeholders and target groups about the project.

Traditional research outputs like research articles will be complemented with innovative dissemination to boost impact; for example, by preparing non-specialist summaries, press releases, blog posts, and visual/video abstracts to better reach INTEGER target audiences.

In addition, a framework and strategy for the large-scale implementation of the intervention will be produced to provide information on organisational and resource requirements, necessary to promote transferability to other contexts. Participation at external events and conferences also help to establish national and international connections with a wide range of stakeholders and engage in on-line or face-to-face communication. In particular, digital technologies (e.g. webinars) will contribute to reach and involve citizens who would otherwise remain out of reach for traditional methods of scientific dissemination

2.7 Open access procedures

INTEGER will ensure Open Access by publishing in open peer-reviewed scientific publications and depositing them in a trusted repository at the time of publication or before through pre-prints, under CC BY (or equivalent), as well as informing via the repository about any research output or any other instruments needed to validate the reached scientific conclusions (mainly Zenodo and SocArXiv).

3 STAKEHOLDER ANALYSIS & ENGAGEMENT PLAN

The INTEGER Consortium has built upon an initial stakeholder scoping exercise undertaken for the proposal, to develop a more definitive analysis of the project's key stakeholders who could have an interest in the activities and results of the INTEGER project and design a focused engagement strategy for them.

Identifying and defining this target audience, as well as a tailored engagement strategy, help to ensure the effectiveness of dissemination activities and the full exploitation of results.

3.1 Stakeholder analysis

A preliminary analysis of the stakeholders has been performed leading to the identification of the following categories of actors, all represented in the consortium composition and/or in the groups of actors to be engaged. The table below summarises the WHO (stakeholder category), the WHY (rationale for engagement), the HOW (engagement preferred modalities) and the WHAT (type of content) per each of them.

WHY	HOW	WHAT
Social Innovators and Citizens, NGO and non-formal active groups		
They are the core beneficiaries of INTEGER and of the innovations developed, as well as the benefits that will spur from them.	They will be engaged through targeted communication, especially through co-creation activities and targeted communication,	Inputs for establishing main societal challenges. Feedback on concepts and guidelines. Social and Digital innovations designed & developed.
PUBLIC Public authorities, municipalities, regions and policy makers		
They can leverage awareness about gains coming from innovation ecosystems, and secure engagement, build capacity and foster adoption.	Targeted workshops to present project results and recommendations.	Inputs for further exploitation and upscale, namely engaging organisations external to the consortium.
INDUSTRY Technology providers, incubators, accelerators, other business actors		
Provide innovative tools and services that meet the needs of citizens.	Targeted workshops to present project results and recommendations.	Input to the validation and development of deployment models, as well as business models for upscale.

Standardisation bodies and open-source communities		
They create consensus around the issues related to new developments and enable continuous innovation through open-source projects.	Targeted workshops to present project results, collecting inputs and recommendations for enhancement.	Inputs for further exploitation and upscale.
Research organisations and universities		
Understanding of the status in research and innovation, leading to advance on the state-of -the-art.	Involvement in the design phase of the research.	Feedback on concepts and tools.
Regulatory bodies		
Both international and national bodies in the partnership countries, when relevant.	Targeted workshops to present project results, collecting inputs and recommendations enhancement.	Inputs for further approval and integration on services and policies.
International networks and initiatives		
Relevant international multi-stakeholder initiatives.	Targeted workshops to present project results, collect inputs and develop synergies.	Input to the validation and development of deployment models.

Table 5: INTEGER preliminary stakeholders' analysis

Based on the stakeholder's mapping, a definition of the communication channels to be used with each was drafted, considering the main stakeholders of each ecosystem and at international level.

Stakeholders	Level of engagement	Key communication & dissemination channels							
		Website	Social media	Press releases	Events	Newsletters	Leaflets	Recommendations	Meetings
Citizens	High	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Public authorities and policy makers	Medium	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Technology providers	Medium	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Standardisation bodies	Medium		X	X		X		X	
Third sector	High	X	X	X	X	X			X
Other industry	Medium	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Academia	Medium	X	X	X	X	X			

Regulators	Low	X	X	X	X				
Other local stakeholders	Medium	X	X	X	X	X		X	X

Table 6: Stakeholder analysis

3.2 Stakeholder engagement

After determining the main stakeholders, the consortium identified them through their power, influence, and interest in what the project is developing. This analysis was essential to organise the interest of the stakeholders in the project and describe the engagement plan. The Power Interest Grid was developed to help with these stakeholders' segregation². When stakeholders are mapped on a power/interest grid, it is possible to determine who has high or low power to affect the project, and who has a high or low interest. The Power Interest Grid tool is divided by quadrants in a matrix, one side the power and on the other side the interest. It is necessary to identify if the stakeholder/s has/have high or low power and high or low interest. Depending on the place the actor is located, the actions that the project will take will be different³. An organisation with high power needs to be kept satisfied, so their opinions must be heard and implemented, while stakeholders with high interest need to be kept informed. If the organisation has both, it is necessary to manage its expectations very closely.

Table 7: Power Interest Grid

This analysis was important for the first approach of the engagement plan. With this matrix, it is possible to identify and start to understand the most important stakeholders.

² MINDTOOLS. Stakeholder Analysis. Available at: https://www.mindtools.com/pages/article/newPPM_07.htm

³ Mendelow, A. L., "Environmental Scanning--The Impact of the Stakeholder Concept" (1981). ICIS 1981 Proceedings. Paper 20. <http://aisel.aisnet.org/icis1981/20>

For the first approach, the partners identified the following stakeholders and selected their power and interest in the project. This initial analysis is described in the following table:

Table 8: Power Interest Grid

The stakeholder analysis and engagement strategy, presented in Table 8, identifies the aim of engaging with each stakeholder, whether for communication, dissemination, or both, as well as the specific rationale for engagement with each stakeholder group, and sets out clearly why INTEGER needs to communicate and/or disseminate its activities, benefits, and outcomes with these target audiences.

The Consortium considers the level of engagement required with each of the stakeholder groups for Year 1 (high/ medium/ low) and acknowledges that these engagement levels may change as the project progresses and moves through different phases e.g., from awareness raising to dissemination of INTEGER outcomes.

The Consortium has devised an engagement strategy, tailored to each stakeholder group, identifying the key communication and dissemination channels that will be used to engage with these groups, again presented in Table 1. The key messages to be communicated are presented in paragraph 3.5.

As it is possible to see in the previous table, project partners identified the main types of stakeholders and rated the level of engagement. Thus, an engagement plan will be outlined according to the decision.

4 COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION TOOLS & CHANNELS

The Consortium is making use of several channels and activities to communicate and/or disseminate INTEGER at local, regional, national and international levels. Some of these have already been developed and their use has become consolidated practice for the partners; others will be included for the strategy of Year 2.

4.1 Internal communications

INTEGER partners use a mixture of emails and networking tools to manage internal communication and information exchanges within the Consortium as follows, namely:

- Sharing documents, design and development activities – Google Drive and emails.
- Communication between partners - Global.network
- Online meetings – Google Meet, Zoom.

The project coordination will be done through the developed section in the local.network platform. Each WP has a specific space for partners to interact and upload all information so that the project progress is easily traceable.

4.2 Project identity

The basis of the project identity consists of a logo, developed by SHINE and supported by a palette of colours and fonts.

Figure 5: INTEGER logos

To guide the partners and provide a coherent image in all materials and communication, SHINE developed an INTEGER Visual Identity Manual. The [Manual](#) is available in Google Drive shared folder and provides the necessary information on the correct use of the logo, their variations and colour pallet.

Figure 6: INTEGER visual identity manual

4.3 Communication materials and templates

INTEGER has created standard templates to be used by the Consortium partners to promote consistency and coherence in branding and communications. These include:

- [Word templates](#) – general document and template for project deliverables

Figure 7: INTEGER word template

- [Powerpoint template](#) for project presentations:

Figure 8: INTEGER power point template

- [Word template for meetings agenda and minutes:](#)

INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

<Project Management Meeting / Monthly Meeting / Other name>	
DATE	<DD Month YYYY> - <HH:mm am/pm CET>
LINK	Meeting link
PROJECT	INTEGER Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions

OBJECTIVES OF THE MEETING • Objective

AGENDA

ATTENDEES

• XX

OPEN ACTION POINTS
(Includes list of action points of previous meetings and this meeting!)

DATE	PARTNER	DESCRIPTION

 Funded by the European Union

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MEETING REPORT/MINUTES

1. WPK | Title of the work-package

- **Agenda point 1 (responsible partner)**

Summary of the discussion.

ACTION POINTS:

--	--

2. WPK | Title of the work-package

- **Agenda point 2 (responsible partner)**

Summary of the discussion.

ACTION POINTS:

--	--

APPROVED ON/BY: XX

 Funded by the European Union

Figure 9: INTEGER word meeting template

4.4 Website

The website collects analytics on visits and overall website activity. This means that we can analyse website activity and use the data to continuously refine the Communication Plan to ensure the effectiveness of communication activities.

Figure 10: INTEGER Website

All other INTEGER communication channels signpost the audience to the project website, which features the latest up to date information on the project.

4.5 Social Media

Social networks play an important role in getting the public interested in the INTEGER project, so that public participation will be maximised as much as possible.

LinkedIn and Twitter accounts have been created for the INTEGER project. These networks will communicate project announcements and developments in short bite-sized messages suitable for this type of media, and different social networks will be used to address different target audiences. They also help to share posts and articles written for the project website, as they will give the audience a taste of the article and then directly link them to the website for the full publication.

Moreover, as well as 'pushing' information out, the social media channels of the partner organisations will be actively used, providing different opportunities for stakeholders to engage with the project, and will encourage open dialogue on INTEGER.

Figure 11: INTEGER social media

4.6 Partner website and social media

The Consortium partners promote the INTEGER project to their own audience and networks, by presenting it on their organisation's website, as shown on the websites below.

Figure 12: SHINE 2Europe web site print – INTEGER on partner website

Partners' social networks also play an important role in sharing INTEGER posts and activities. They individually post information about INTEGER in such a way as to drive traffic towards the website and gather interest in the various online communities.

All partners actively participate in sharing INTEGER news on LinkedIn and Twitter. When managing their organisation's accounts, partners:

- Retweet all the posts produced by @INTEGER;
- Use the hashtags #INTEGER and #INTEGER_EU every time they tweet in English or their own language, or retweet INTEGER news;
- If possible, tag all the partners, or at least the ones that are directly related to the content of the tweet.

Figure 13: Examples of posts about INTEGER in social media

Optimising the partners' social networks in this way has a multiplier effect in reaching an increased audience.

4.7 General media

The Consortium engages with the general media through the circulation of press releases aimed at the general public. These disclose the results of the project's activities so that all stakeholders are aware of.

A press release was made in April 2023 in English and translated to all partner languages.

4.8 Newsletters

INTEGER newsletters will be developed and circulated to all those registering their interest on the project website.

In addition, the Consortium partners use their networks, adhering to GDPR guidelines, to garner and raise interest in the project, to increase the number of stakeholders registering their interest in the project and the size of the overall INTEGER mailing list.

The newsletter has been designed using the visual identity manual and will be issued every 4 months (6 in total over the project lifetime). In year 1 three newsletters will be released:

Newsletter	Month	Year	Content
1	May	2023	Dissemination of KO; of the 3 ecosystem visits with details; announcement of the pre-event (what is the event and what are the objectives?, when and where will take place, to whom?, who is going to organise it?)
2	September	2023	Dissemination of the model event that took place on 17th - 18th May (what is the event and what are the objectives? When and where will it take place, to whom? Who is going to organise it?, photos)
3	January	2024	Dissemination of the regional event (Catalonia, Spain) (what is the event and what are the objectives? When and where will it take place, to whom? Who is going to organise it?, photos)
			Dissemination of the regional event (Hamburg, Germany) (what is the event and what are the objectives? When and where will it take place, to whom? Who is going to organise it?, photos)
			Dissemination of the regional event (Krakow, Poland) (what is the event and what are the objectives? When and where will it take place, to whom? Who is going to organise it?, photos)
4	May	2024	Dissemination of the final event(what is the event and what are the objectives? When and where will it take place, to whom? Who is going to organise it?, photos)
5	October	2024	News of the project
6	January	2025	Overview of the results of the project

Table 6: INTEGER newsletter plan

4.9 Printed material

SHINE has developed an INTEGER flyer/leaflet to present an overview of the project for a general audience, its objectives, expected impacts and the Consortium partners in a visually appealing way. This printed material will be reviewed as the project progresses, and more information can be added on results and outcomes if appropriate. It is available in all partnership languages.

INTEGER
 INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

CREATING COL-LABORATORIES FOR IMPROVED BUSINESS OPPORTUNITIES OF SOCIAL INNOVATION

This Horizon Europe project INTEGER (February 2023 to January 2025) aims to bring together actors from 3H and 4H systems to face common challenges: the "co-laboratories", a next generation of living labs, a cooperative instrument based on a peer-to-peer approach between business-driven economic innovation and social-driven innovation.

WHY?

There are approximately 2 million social economy enterprises in Europe, representing 10% of all businesses in the EU. Achieving the triple transition "green, digital and social" demands a paramount effort for including, in a more decisive manner, social economy enterprises, social innovators and entrepreneurs in our EU innovation ecosystems.

By improving the business opportunities of social innovators, INTEGER seeks to accelerate new win-win games, local mission-driven synergies, groundbreaking coordination of actions, governance, implementation, uptaking and exploitation dynamics, focusing on challenge-driven promotion of healthy living and well-being.

WHAT?

INTEGER wants to generate synergies by creating an EU Healthy Living Co-laboratory (common open house of all kinds of innovators and entrepreneurs interested in producing new products and services that come from business or social-oriented innovation) on healthy living innovations based on the inclusion of social innovation actors. A true network of networks' community with the capacity to work on real social, tech and business-driven projects.

This will be done after to develop economic, social and digital innovation skills and exchange of best practices across the INTEGER and pilot and wider community and the experienced members of three regional ecosystems (Catalonia - Spain, Hamburg - Germany, Krakow - Poland). And to be ready to scale and replicate the 4H COL-LABORATORIES, including its availability for widespread use in regional and European policy actions and implementation initiatives.

COL-LABORATIONS

Co-laborations will be held in 3 EU Regions - Catalonia, Hamburg and Krakow - to foster social innovation Minimum Viable Products and Services to upscale it throughout Europe.

INTEGER 4H MODEL

INTEGER 4H model implementing guide will be created with dedicated materials to support the co-creation of co-laboratories as an integrative innovation model attending to the EU social, digital and green transitions.

Sessions with Special Interests Groups will develop pathways and network strategies for the uptake of the model.

INTEGRATING 3H AND 4H MODELS FOR A EUROPEAN INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS TRANSITION

INTEGER
 For a Green, Digital, Social transition

Technologies for business
 ECONOMIC-CENTRED INNOVATION

National Innovation Ecosystems
 Industrial clusters
 Technology Parks
 Incubators, accelerators, startups
 Risk-capital
 Business Entrepreneurship

Technologies for society
 SOCIAL-CENTRED INNOVATION

Place-based Innovation Ecosystems
 Social Digital Innovation
 Living Labs, social labs, co-laboratories
 Co-design, co-creation methods
 Citizen-centred Innovation
 Social entrepreneurship

Digital Technologies and Networks

WHAT IS INTEGER?

INTEGER aims to bring together actors from 3H and 4H systems to face common challenges: the "co-laboratories", a next generation of living labs, a cooperative instrument based on a peer-to-peer approach between business-driven economic innovation and social-driven innovation.

WHAT DO WE AIM TO ACHIEVE?

Focused on challenge-driven promotion of healthy living, INTEGER will bring forward three important innovations for the development of more robust, sustainable, inclusive, and integrative EU innovation ecosystems:

- ▶ The INTEGER 4 Helix Co-laboratory model to implement the next generation of living labs, the "Co-laboratory",
- ▶ An EU Healthy Living Co-laboratory, a true network of networks' community with capacity to work on real social, tech and business-driven projects, and
- ▶ A new professional profile, the "co-lab" or "co-laboratory manager" as a multiplying agent of change of these integrated innovation ecosystems.

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 Social entrepreneurship

Digital Technologies and Networks

FOLLOW US & FIND OUT MORE

integercollab.eu [/integercollab](https://www.linkedin.com/company/integercollab) [/INTEGERcollab](https://twitter.com/INTEGERcollab)

PROJECT PARTNERS

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Figure 14: INTEGER Leaflet

INTEGER
 INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

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Figure 15: INTEGER Roll-up and poster

4.10 Project video

In order to document the INTEGER “col.laboratory effect”, to scale up and replicate in other EU regions and for other EU challenges, the partners will prepare and disseminate 8 video pills with partners and 5 with experts / policy makers, under AFE leadership.

The partners involved will prepare a plan, describing who is in charge and the calendar to disseminate the videos.

4.11 Col.laborathons

The partners will organise the “Col.laborathons”, one general and three regionals ‘col.laborathons’, plus the active participation of project partners in brother/sister projects coordination meetings, and existing networks’ events to exchange, learn, systematise information, test the INTEGER 4 H model, contrast, enrich, disseminate, upscale and actively promote implementation and uptake in other regions and sectors.

4.12 Scientific and conference publications

Participation of the INTEGER consortium members in national and international conferences will spread the project’s value and interact directly with the audiences. Although those events will be selected every year according to the focus and stage of the project.

4.13 Events, Conferences and other dissemination opportunities

Project partners will actively participate in relevant regional, national and international conferences and events, where they communicate the activities and disseminate the results of the project through presentations, speaking and exhibition opportunities.

Participation In Conferences, Capacity Building Programmes And Meetings	
Open Living Labs Days of the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) Capacity Building ENoLL through the ENoLL Virtual Learning Platform	Knowledge exchange and project partnerships between +480 members in Europe and worldwide through the ENoLL capacity building programme and targeted working groups
Biannual ESSI Conference European School on Social Innovation (ESSI)	Preparation of a targeted session on social innovation ecosystems
European Cluster Alliance (ECA)’s virtual morning meetings to present project progress European Cluster Collaboration Platform (ECCP)	To raise awareness and enrich the INTEGER_4H Collaboratory model with the community of cluster organisations worldwide (over 1,200) through presentation of results in at ECCP morning sessions

Annual Meeting of the World Leisure Organisation (WLO)	To disseminate results in the Cultural and Creative Industries Sector
Annual Conference of Network for Advancing & Evaluating the Societal Impact of Science (AESIS)	To disseminate results and contrast with other organisations interested in maximising social impact
General Meeting with FDSUT, Fondation pour le Développement du Service Universel de Télécommunications. Senegal	Enlarging impact to other regions of the world
In Catalonia, presentation of the INTEGER community in the annual Mobile World Congress 2023 in Barcelona	Maximise the impact of the INTEGER community in the global mobile industry.
Hamburg yearly conference "Fachtagung Sozialwirtschaft" addresses the development and innovation in the social economy at Hamburg's senates chancellery. Annual event that addresses EU funded projects in the town hall. INTEGER results will be presented in regular meetings of the Ministry of Social Affairs	These conferences address the development and innovation in the social economy and stakeholders' integration. Different stakeholders from the public administration, politics, universities, civil society organisations and private companies regularly participate in this event.
In Krakow, there is an event organised every year, called Open Eyes Economy Summit, with the focus on societal/economic/climate challenges.	The project results could be channelled through this yearly conference.
In connection to SHAFE/NET4, a training school (TS) and two events will be organised within the scope and programme of the COST Action.	The events and TS will have the potential to reach the 51 countries in the COST Action and will be used to present INTEGER results, promote and scale-up activities to other countries/regions

Table 9: Conferences, Capacity Building Programmes and Meetings

4.14 INTEGER study group

This group aims to identify potential topics for research and publications and share these results with the rest of the consortium. As this is not a research project, it is a parallel task to potentialize the project results. The initial INTEGER Study Group is represented as follows:

Integer partner	Members
i2CAT	Toni Caro Marcos Doespiritusanto
URV	Mercedes Teruel

URV	Xavier Càmara
URV	Xiaoni Li
SHINE	Carina Dantas
SHINE	Natália Machado
AFE	Willeke van Staalduinen
AFE	Jonas Bernitt
AFE	Patricia Lucha

Table 10: INTEGER study group – potential members

The group will meet at least three times a year. As the first task, they will prepare guidelines to publications and will work accordingly on the communication and dissemination plan.

4.15 Webinars

The INTEGER project aims to address the deep existing gap between social innovators and entrepreneurs and their regional innovation ecosystems to fully harness the potential of EU innovation in the critical policy area of healthy living. To engage the stakeholders, a series of 3 exchange webinars will be prepared to learn from integration experiences of social innovation actors in innovation ecosystems.

4.16 Partner networks

The Consortium partners are active in a variety of European and international networks related to the wider active and healthy ageing field. Partners use these networks as a further means of sharing project information and disseminating results to optimise the visibility of INTEGER.

Examples of the networks in which partners are actively involved include:

- **NET4Age-Friendly:** Carina Dantas, from Consortium partner SHINE, is Action Chair and Willeke van Staalduinen from partner AFE is Vice-Chair. The main aim of NET4Age-Friendly is to establish an international and interdisciplinary network of researchers from all sectors to foster awareness, and to support the creation and implementation of smart, healthy indoor and outdoor environments for present and future generations.
- **European Covenant on Demographic Change:** Carina Dantas, from Consortium partner SHINE, is the Vice-President, so INTEGER is well-placed to leverage this network which joins more than 160 public authorities, civil society organisations and businesses, coming from different European countries, all committed to cooperate and implement evidence-based solutions to support active and healthy ageing as a comprehensive answer to Europe's demographic challenge.
- **Thematic Network SHAFE – Smart Healthy Age-Friendly Environments:** Carina Dantas (SHINE) and Willeke van Staalduinen (AFE) are Coordinators of this network which gathers over 170 partners across Europe that have endorsed a Joint Statement with the

main policy recommendations on the area, delivered to the European Commission and Member States in November 2018.

- EIC Community
- KIC Health
- EIP on AHA reference sites
- ENOLL-European Network of Living Labs;
- ESSI-European School of Social Innovation
- Col.lab.cat community
- Gesundheitswirtschaft Hamburg Gmb
- eHealth-Network
- Investment Bank Hamburg (IFB)
- Health Innovation Port (HIP)
- Krakow Living Lab (KLL)
- Małopolska Bio-Region

4.17 INTEGER Hub News & Interviews

The INTEGER consortium gives the highest importance to communication for the success of the project. Visualisation and adaptation of the communication tools and products to the key target groups of the project will guide the whole outreach effort put in place by the consortium.

As part of the project, the partners will develop a INTEGER platform hub, that will include a collection of good practices to merge lessons learned into start drafting a novel integrated model.

The platform will be used as a tool to disseminate the news, “hubposts”, “zoom” issue-specific articles and interviews.

4.18 Dissemination reporting

SHINE has developed an [Excel file](#) to report all of the activities within communication and dissemination, which is stored in the Google Drive of the project and is regularly updated by all partners. Periodic reports of the current achievement of KPIs and details on the activities developed are presented by SHINE in the consortium meetings for monitoring and re-planning if necessary.

Table 11: Excel for comms activities reporting

5 CONCLUSION

The INTEGER Consortium is seriously committed to implementing this comprehensive Communication & Dissemination Plan. It is a key component in the overall INTEGER strategy to ensure the sustainability of the services and outputs developed by the project, both during and beyond the end of the funding period.

This plan will be monitored regularly to ensure that it continues to meet the evolving needs of the project, as it moves from awareness-raising to targeting scientific dissemination and reaching out to industry.

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APPENDIX 1: INITIAL LIST OF SPECIFIC TARGET STAKEHOLDERS

The Consortium has compiled an initial list of specific target stakeholders within the categories defined in the Stakeholder analysis, and these are presented below. Each regional partner team is responsible for preparing a comprehensive stakeholders' map, starting with key stakeholders to participate in the first actions of the project.

The list was compiled through a mix of desk research and partner feedback and provides a starting point as the project commences for targeted communication. It will be reviewed and added to as the project progresses. The emails are kept internally for reasons of data protection.

Table 12 - initial list of specific target stakeholders⁴

Cracow		
4 H areas	Level of impact	Stakeholder
Government	National	The Polish Ministry of Health
	Regional	Marshall Office of Malopolska Region
	Local	Municipality Centre of Social Assistance
Civic Society	National	Polish National Initiative for Collaboration of Senior Councils
	Regional	Krakow Smog Alert
	Local	Senior Activity Centres
Industry	National	Polish Confederation Lewiatan
	Regional	Klaster Lifescience
	Local	DIABMED
Academia	National	Polish National Gerontological Association
	Regional	University of Science and technology Krakow
	Local	Faber Education Centre
Hamburg		
4 H areas	Level of impact	Stakeholder
Government	Regional	Hamburg Ministry of Social Affairs

⁴ This list is just a sample of key stakeholders, none of the cases are exhaustive lists.

		Hamburg Ministry of Economy
		Hamburg Ministry of Science
Civic Society	Regional	Max und Ingeborg Herz Stiftung (Foundation)
		Patriotische Gesellschaft (Philanthropic civil society organisation)
Industry	National	Aidhere
		Philips
	Regional	Health Innovation Port
Academia	Regional	University Hospital Hamburg
		University Hamburg
		Hamburg University of Applied Science
Other	Regional	Hamburg Investment Bank
		Cluster Agency Gesundheitswirtschaft Hamburg GmbH
4helix	Regional	Arbeitskreis nachhaltige Stadtgesundheit (transdisciplinary working group, Civil Society, Academia, Government, Economy)
Catalonia		
4 H areas	Level of impact	Type of Stakeholder
Government	Regional	Health department - Catalonian government
		Social & Family Department - Catalonian government
		Labour & Digital Society Department - Catalonian government
Civic Society	Local	Patient Associations
		Consell Català de la gent gran
		Association of "AMPA" Mothers and fathers of primary schools
		Neighbourhood associations
Industry	Regional	Giromed Institute
		Me Mima Baby
	National	Bax & Company
		Eurecat
		Saluscoop

Academia	Regional	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)
		Universitat Rovira i Virgili (URV)
		Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB)
		Universitat Barcelona (UB)
International Stakeholders		
4 H areas		Type of Stakeholder
Government		DG Employment & Social inclusion
Civic Society		Age platform Europe
Industry		European Business & innovation Network
		Phillips Health innovation port ; Gaia AG
Academia		UNA Europa
		NET4Age COST action